

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20133142

Impact Of School Community Relationship On Management Of Public Secondary Schools In North Central, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of school community relationship on management of public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria. Seven research questions guided the study. Seven hypotheses were tested for the study. The researcher adopted descriptive survey research design. The population was 42,235 teachers from 6,601 public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria. A sample of 845 respondents was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled “School Community Relationship and Decision Making Questionnaire (SCRDMQ)”. It was a 15-item questionnaire on four point rating scale. The questionnaire was validated by three experts. Two experts in Educational Management Unit of Educational Foundations and one expert in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, all in the Faculty of Education, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. It was trial-tested on 40 teachers who were part of the population but not part of the sampled population. The result of the trial-test yielded a reliability coefficient value of 0.77. Data were analyzed using the descriptive statistics of Mean Score and Standard Deviations to answer the research questions while Chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that School community relationship has no significant impact on provision of fund, provision of physical facilities and provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. It was concluded that school community relationship impact positively on management of public secondary schools in terms of provision of fund, provision of physical facilities and provision of instructional materials in North Central Nigeria. The study therefore recommended among others that. The government should allocate adequate funds to schools and ensure timely disbursement while fostering collaboration with communities through supportive policies. This partnership can lead to joint fundraising efforts, resulting in increased financial resources for developmental projects such as constructing classrooms and paying staff salaries. Such synergy not only alleviates financial pressure but also strengthens the trust between schools and communities in North Central, Nigeria.

Keywords: school community relationship, provision of fund, provision of physical facilities and provision of instructional materials

INTRODUCTION

Management is essential machinery for the success of any organization be it private or public. However, management of public secondary schools faces multifaceted challenges globally, regionally and locally, though their intensity varies by context. Worldwide, school administrators contend with inadequate funding, rapid policy changes, teacher shortages, increasing student diversity, technological demands, and accountability pressures tied to standardized testing and performance metrics (Yedeji, 2018). In West Africa, these global challenges are compounded by chronic underfunding, weak infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, limited instructional materials, poor teacher motivation, and political interference in school administration, alongside socio-economic issues such as poverty and insecurity that disrupt schooling (Yedeji, 2018). In North Central Nigeria specifically, management of public secondary schools is further constrained by inconsistent government funding, deteriorating facilities, shortages of qualified teachers, frequent industrial actions, insecurity and communal conflicts, weak supervision, and limited capacity for strategic planning, all of which collectively hinder effective school leadership, instructional quality, and students' academic outcomes (Ugwanyi, 2015).

Management of public secondary schools is therefore seen as the mobilization, coordination, harmonization and utilization of public secondary school resources for the achievement of public secondary school goals and objectives (Saiti & Saitis, 2015). Management of public secondary schools can also be seen as the judicious utilization of human, financial and material resources of public secondary schools towards the achievement of its goals (Akpakwu, 2012). Public secondary schools are the post primary institutions of learning established and managed by government, communities or religious bodies to provide learners with functional education in order to become useful for themselves, the society and for higher education (Saiti & Saitis, 2015).

In North Central Nigeria, there are many public secondary schools which seem to contribute in no small measure to the educational development in Nigeria through provision of manpower for the nation. These public secondary schools are managed by government who take major responsibility in the management of public educational institutions in Nigeria (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). However, it is worthy to note that management of public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria in recent times, appears to face numerous challenges such as inadequate funding, school facilities, instructional materials, security challenges and many others. Anthony, Yara and Pev (2017) lament over some of the challenges facing management of secondary education in Nigeria noting that there is inadequate conducive classrooms, office accommodations in some schools while in some schools, books in the libraries are obsolete and laboratory equipment are in the state of disrepair. This situation in North Central Nigeria seems to make it difficult for the realization of the essence of establishing secondary schools.

School community relationship is a two-way symbiotic arrangement through which the school and the community cooperate with each other for the realization of the goals of the school and the community (Okwori & Ede, 2012). The success or failure of public secondary schools depends to a large extent on the level of relationship they maintain with their host communities. This makes it demanding on the school managers to identify the key areas of relationship between their schools and the host communities (Miller, 2011). Moreover, it may be seen that schools in pursuit of quality education, will require a lot of human, material and financial resources for building the capacity of the education system to be able to deliver high quality and relevant curriculum to learners of all ages. However, school administrators alone cannot achieve this objective. It requires the cooperation of the school and the host community. This implies that, for effective management of public secondary schools, there is need for school community relationship.

School community relationship exists in different areas where the community and school are mutually exclusive of the benefits of such relationships. In the management of public secondary schools, Okam and Bozimo (2014, p.235) identify funding, provision of physical facilities, instructional materials, dissemination of information and organization of training as contribution to the management of schools. Similarly, Okwori and Ede (2012, p.116) highlight areas of school community relationship such as

involvement of community members in decision making, provision of security services, sharing of resources, provision of students' scholarship awards and participation in orientation programmes. This study focuses on provision of funds, physical facilities, instructional materials, students' scholarship awards, security services, sharing of resources and involvement in decision making as major areas of school community relationship which seem to influence management of public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria.

Fund is a pool of money that is allocated for a specific purpose or it is the amount of money that is available to be spent, especially money that is given to an organization or person for a particular purpose (Idoko, Ogwuche & Ameh (2015). Provision of fund therefore entails making available funds to school for effective and efficient management. Provision of fund is one of the areas school community relationship could exist which may affect either positively or negatively the management of public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. When there is good relationship between school and community, the community may organize fund raising committee to help raise fund for the execution of projects in the school. This is mostly done through School Based Management Committee (SBMC) and Parent Teachers Associations (PTA). Where there is poor school community relationship, there may be a challenge of community provision of funds and this may affect management of public secondary schools in different dimensions including provision of physical facilities.

Provision of physical facilities is essential in the management of public secondary schools. Physical facilities comprise the physical expression of the school curriculum in the construction, internal and external arrangements of the buildings, equipment, grounds, surroundings, general appearance which includes the flower beds, paths, orchards, shrubs, playgrounds, classrooms, assembly hall, dining hall, desks and school farms (Uko, 2015). These facilities provide a comfortable atmosphere for the achievement of educational goals. In a school system where there is inadequate provision of physical facilities effective teaching and learning may hardly take place and this may negatively affect management of such a school. School community relationship may help in the provision of school physical facilities such as construction of classroom blocks, office blocks, libraries, laboratories and it may also help in provision of teaching aids, tables, chairs, technological devices like computers, printers among others. The provision of these physical facilities may boost the state of instructional materials.

Provision of instructional materials is necessary for management of public secondary schools if the objective of teaching and learning is to be achieved. This is because instructional materials assist teachers and learners to teach and learn effectively. Instructional materials are objects or devices that assist the teachers to present their lessons logically and sequentially to the learners. Oluwagbohunmi and Abdu-Raheem (2014) acknowledge that instructional materials are such items or devices used by teachers to aid explanations and make learning of subject matter understandable to students during teaching and learning process. A cordial relationship between the school and community could enable the community members to contribute textbooks, chalk or bold pens, projectors, computers to various schools within their communities to support management of such schools. However, absence of communities support in provision of instructional materials may affect the management of public secondary with such communities. Poor school community relationship may even affect both the community and school in many areas including use of resources. It is against this background that the study sought to investigate the impact of school community relationship on management of public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria laying emphasis on provision of fund, physical facilities and instructional materials.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, attempts made by government over the years through educational policies to improve management of public secondary schools especially in North Central Nigeria appears to have failed. The management of public secondary schools under an idea situation are expected to enjoy adequate funding, provision of physical facilities, instructional materials, use of materials resources, sustained security and effective decision making. However, the researcher and relevant stakeholders in public secondary schools such as federal and state ministries of education, school administrators, parents and community members

observed that management of public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria has been under condition of gross ineffectiveness. This ineffectiveness may be as a result of school community relationship. It has also been observed by the researcher that many public secondary schools seem to loss support from host communities in the area of provision of physical facilities, instructional materials while others do not seem to enjoy good community relationship where community members could utilize their material resources such as halls and the schools would make use of community material resources for school activities. More so, it appears that few or none of the community members are involved in decision making in public secondary schools for better management and government of public secondary schools. This situation seems to affect effective functioning of public secondary schools in North Central thus the objectives of these seem to be hardly realized. It is based on the above background that the researcher was motivated to find out the impact of school community relationship on management of public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of school community relationship on management of public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria. Specially, the study seeks to:

1. ascertain the impact of school community relationship on provision of funds in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.
2. determine the impact of school community relationship on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools.
3. examine the impact of school community relationship on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the impact of school community relationship on provision of funds in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of school community relationship on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools?
3. What is the impact of school community relationship on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. School community relationship has no significant impact on provision of funds in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.
2. School community relationship has no significant impact on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools.
3. School community relationship has no significant impact on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools.

Literature Review

Social exchange theory is a sociological and psychological theory which was developed by American social psychologists John Thibaut and Karold Kelley from 1917. The theory studies the social behaviour in the interaction of two parties that implement a cost-benefit analysis to determine risks and benefits. The theory also involves economic relationships, the cost-benefit analysis occurs when each party has goods that the other parties value. Thibaut and Kelley based their theory on small groups related with dyadic relationships. They used the reward-cost matrices from Game Theory and discovered some clues of individuals' interdependence such as the power of a party over each other, also known as the "correspondence" versus "non-correspondence" of outcomes. Additionally, they suggest that an individual can unilaterally affect his or her own outcomes in a relationship through chosen behaviours. They could predict the possible course of a social interaction through the analysis of aspects of power in

an encounter. They also experimented on how the outcomes received in a relationship could define a person's attractions to relationships.

School community relationship exists in different ways and which of which is provision of funds. Funds to a layman means a sum of money earmark for execution of projects or programmes in a given organization. Therefore, the act or process of making funds available for the purpose of executing organizational projects or programmes could referred to as provision of funds. Hornby, Wemeier, McIntosh and Turnbull (2015) maintain that provision of funds is the process of providing resources usually in form of money or other values such as effort or time for a project, a person, a business by either private or public institutions. Provision of funds also means money for a particular purpose and the act of providing money for such a purpose. Government shoulders the responsibility of proviso of funds for educational institutions in Nigeria. Hinchliffe (2012) sates that an average of two-third of all state government expenditure is allocated to educational institutions. However, other stakeholders such as community also participation in provision of funds to support management of educational institutions since it is assumed that the funds provided by government could not cater for all financial needs of educational institutions.

School facilities are important at any level of education. School facilities play a major role in creating an enabling environment for work, teaching and learning as well as the conduct of other educational activities. They refer to all the buildings and equipment in the school that aid teaching and learning, including school ground. Akpan (2011) describes school facilities as essential materials that have to be provided and properly managed for the successful execution of the school curriculum. Akpan further stresses that the school manager needs to determine the physical facilities need of the school and provide the financial resources for procurement and management of the facilities. Bua (2020) maintains that the school manager has to develop good programmes for operation and maintenance of the facilities and has to be able to provide custodial staff and supervise them to ensure proper maintenance of the facilities. Policies need be developed to ensure orderly and proper use of school facilities.

School community relationship can be seen in various ways including provision of instructional materials to aid teaching and learning in schools. Instructional materials are defined as those materials used for practical and demonstration in the class situation by students and teachers (Ibeneme, 2012). They are those objects or devices that assist the teacher to present a lesson to the learners in a logical and manner (Ikerionwu, 2015). At the secondary level of education, school community relationship takes the form of provision of instructional as argued by (Mammam, 2016). Instructional materials are essential facilities needed for teaching and learning of to promote teachers' efficiency and improve students' performance. The provision and use of instructional materials make learning more interesting, practical, realistic and appealing. Instructional materials also enable both the teachers and students to participate actively and effectively in lesson sessions. Adequate and proper use of instructional materials gives room for acquisition of skills and knowledge and development of self- confidence and self- actualization.

RESULTS

A total of 845 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents. However, 840 representing 99.4% copies of questionnaire were returned by the respondents while five representing 0.6% copies of questionnaire were recorded as attrition. The data obtained from the questionnaire were presented, analyzed and interpreted.

Research Question 1: *What is the impact of school community relationship on provision of fund in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Rating on Impact of School Community Relationship on Provision of Fund in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Community organizes fund raising ceremonies to raise money for school development as a result of her relationship with the school	840	267	337	133	103	2.91	0.98	Agree
2	Through good school community relationship, money donated by the community is used for building of classroom blocks	840	254	345	135	106	2.89	0.97	Agree
3	Community contribute money for purchase of office equipment	840	251	343	126	120	2.86	1.00	Agree
4	Money realized from community donation helps in paying PTA staff salaries	840	253	269	225	93	2.81	0.98	Agree
5	Community provides money to support hosting of sport activities	840	257	221	250	112	2.74	1.03	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.84		Agree

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2026

Table 1 shows mean ratings of 2.91, 2.89, 2.86, 2.81, 2.74 and cluster mean of 2.84 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 0.98, 0.97, 1.00, 0.98 and 1.03 respectively. The result indicated that the respondents agreed that community organizes fund raising ceremonies to raise money for school development as a result of her relationship with the school, through good school community relationship, money donated by the community is used for building of classroom blocks, community contribute money for purchase of office equipment, money realized from community donation helps in paying PTA staff salaries and community provides money to support hosting of sport activities. The cluster mean value of 2.84 was above the mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of school community relationship on provision of fund in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *What is the impact of school community relationship on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Rating on Impact of School Community Relationship on Provision of Physical Facilities in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	Community helps in the provision of students' hostel	840	235	247	257	101	2.73	0.99	Agree
7	Community provides library book shelves	840	238	396	126	80	2.94	0.90	Agree
8	Community provides laboratory equipment	840	244	414	110	72	2.99	0.87	Agree
9	Community helps in the construction of toilets in schools	840	252	403	104	81	2.98	0.90	Agree
10	Community assists in the provision of classroom desks	840	266	376	122	76	2.99	0.90	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.93		Agree

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2026

Table 2 shows mean ratings of 2.73, 2.94, 2.99, 2.98, 2.99 and cluster mean of 2.93 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 0.99, 0.90, 0.87, 0.90 and 0.90 respectively. The result indicated that the respondents agreed that community helps in the provision of students' hostel,

community provides library book shelves, community provides laboratory equipment, community helps in the construction of toilets in schools and community assists in the provision of classroom desks. The cluster mean value of 2.93 was above the mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of school community relationship on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Research Question 3: *What is the impact of school community relationship on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria?*

Table 3: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Rating on Impact of School Community Relationship on Provision of Instructional Materials in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	Community provides interactive board for classroom instruction	840	250	258	223	109	2.77	1.01	Agree
12	Community helps in the provision of projectors for presentation of lessons	840	259	266	197	118	2.79	1.03	Agree
12	Lesson note books are provided by the community to help teachers prepare students' lesson notes	840	278	263	184	115	2.84	1.03	Agree
14	Some subjects' textbooks are provided by the community to enhance effective teaching	840	249	223	247	121	2.71	1.04	Agree
15	Marker pens are provided by the community to help in copying notes on the board	840	260	277	195	108	2.82	1.01	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.79		Agree

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2026

Table 3 shows mean ratings of 2.77, 2.79, 2.84, 2.71, 2.82 and cluster mean of 2.79 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 1.01, 1.03, 1.03, 1.04 and 1.01 respectively. The result indicated that the respondents agreed that community provides interactive board for classroom instruction, community helps in the provision of projectors for presentation of lessons, lesson note books are provided by the community to help teachers prepare students' lesson notes, some subjects' textbooks are provided by the community to enhance effective teaching and marker pens are provided by the community to help in copying notes on the board. The cluster mean value of 2.79 was above the mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of school community relationship on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: School community relationship has no significant impact on provision of fund in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Table 8: Chi-square Analysis of Impact of School Community Relationship on Provision of Fund in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	P	df	χ^2	Decision
SA	256	210	0.000	3	175.029 ^a	Sig.
A	303	210				
D	174	210				
SD	107	210				
Total	840					

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2026

Table 8 shows Chi-square calculated value of 175.029^a at 3 degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that school community relationship has no significant

impact on provision of fund in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This means that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of fund in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: School community relationship has no significant impact on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Table 9: Chi-square Analysis of Impact of School Community Relationship on Provision of Physical Facilities in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	P	df	χ^2	Decision
SA	247	210	0.000	3	76.590 ^a	Sig.
A	367	210				
D	143	210				
SD	83	210				
Total	840					

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2026

Table 9 shows Chi-square calculated value of 76.590^a at 3 degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that school community relationship has no significant impact on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This means that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3: School community relationship has no significant impact on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Table 10: Chi-square Analysis of Impact of School Community Relationship on Provision of Instructional Materials in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	P	df	χ^2	Decision
SA	259	210	0.000	3	67.971 ^a	Sig.
A	258	210				
D	209	210				
SD	114	210				
Total	840					

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2026

Table 10 shows Chi-square calculated value of 67.971^a at 3 degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that school community relationship has no significant impact on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This means that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section presents discussion of findings as follows:

The first finding of the study showed that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of fund in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. This finding signifies communities organize fundraising events to generate funds for school, which is used for constructing classroom blocks, purchasing office equipment, paying salaries of PTA staff, and supporting sports activities hosted by the school. This finding is in line with the findings of Anthony, Yaro and Pev (2017) whose findings showed that Parents' Teachers' Associations, Old Students' Associations, school committees and school board of governors have significant influence on the management of secondary schools in terms of provision funding and decision making. The finding is also in line with the findings of Al Nakpodia (2013) whose study revealed that community provision of funds has significant impact on educational development in Delta State, Nigeria. The researcher also agree that school community

relationship has positive significant impact on provision of fund in public secondary schools because local businesses, alumni associations, and parent-teacher associations (PTAs) contribute significantly to financial support, reducing the financial burden on government and school administrators. This partnership ensures that schools can execute planned projects effectively.

The second finding of the study showed that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. This finding means that communities assist in providing hostels for students, library shelves, laboratory equipment, classroom desks, and toilet facilities, significantly enhancing the school environment. This finding agreed with the findings of Nakpodia (2011) whose findings showed that community provision of physical facilities, instructional materials and use of resources have significant impact on management of public secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District Nigeria. The finding is also in line with the findings of Izuehie and Ofojebe (2019) whose study revealed that communities participate in the provision of building facilities, basic amenities, and teaching resources has positive impact on management of public secondary schools in Enugu State. The researcher also agree that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of physical facilities in public secondary schools because communities play a pivotal role in providing physical facilities, such as classrooms, laboratories, and sports fields. Through collaborative efforts, such as communal labour or resource pooling, community members address infrastructural gaps in schools. These contributions enhance the learning environment, demonstrating the community's commitment to the educational development of their children.

The third finding of the study showed that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. This finding indicated that communities supply interactive boards for teaching, projectors for lesson presentations, lesson notebooks for teachers to prepare students' notes, subject-specific textbooks to improve instruction, and marker pens for classroom use. This finding corresponds with the findings of Uzoechina (2013) whose findings showed that there was significant impact of school community relationship on provision of funds and instructional materials in secondary school in Anambra State, Nigeria. The finding is also in line with the findings of Nakpodia (2011) whose findings revealed that community provision of physical facilities, instructional materials and use of resources have significant impact on management of public secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District Nigeria.. The researcher also agrees that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of instructional materials in public secondary schools because strong school-community relationships encourage the donation of instructional materials like textbooks, laboratory equipment, and teaching aids. Communities recognize the value of education and often step in to supplement government-provided resources. Such involvement ensures students have access to quality learning materials, improving academic outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was established that school community relationship impact positively on management of public secondary schools in terms of provision of fund, provision of physical facilities and provision of instructional materials in North Central, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should allocate adequate funds to schools and ensure timely disbursement while fostering collaboration with communities through supportive policies. This partnership can lead to joint fundraising efforts, resulting in increased financial resources for developmental projects such as constructing classrooms and paying staff salaries. Such synergy not only alleviates financial pressure but also strengthens the trust between schools and communities in North Central, Nigeria.

2. The Ministry of Education should establish frameworks that actively involve communities in infrastructural development through matching grants or incentives for community-driven initiatives. This collaboration will encourage communities to participate in the provision of facilities like classrooms, laboratories, and libraries, ultimately creating a conducive learning environment that reflects shared responsibility and commitment to the growth of public secondary schools in Nigeria.
3. School administrators in public secondary schools should engage community stakeholders in regular dialogues to identify priority needs for instructional materials and coordinate their provision through donations or partnerships. This collaborative effort may ensure the availability of textbooks, ICT tools, and other learning aids, thereby enhancing the quality of teaching and learning while fostering a sense of collective ownership and mutual support in public secondary schools in North Central

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